

The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Customer Engagement: The Case of Zynergia

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between social media marketing and customer engagement within the context of Zynergia. Quota sampling was used which included 53 customers. Through non-experimental quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique, validated questionnaire, Mean, Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) and Multiple Linear Regression; results showed that the level of social media marketing was high or oftentimes manifested. It was also found out that the level of customer engagement was high or oftentimes manifested. There was a significant relationship between social media marketing and customer engagement. This implies that when the social media marketing is high, customers are more likely to engage with the business. This further means that the hub's activities and strategies on social media platforms play a crucial role in fostering interactions and building customer relationships. Accordingly, interaction best influences customer engagement. It was recommended that the management to enhance further interactive engagement by providing staff training for social media interactions and fostering online communities for customer interaction. Future researchers are encouraged to investigate the specific impact of each social media marketing domain on customer engagement.

Keywords: social media marketing, customer engagement, Zynergia, health and wellness hub

1. Introduction

Customer engagement (CE) is fundamental to business success, specifically in today's digital age, where social media marketing (SMM) is critical in fostering these relationships. However, navigating the dynamic social media landscape, crafting engaging content, and measuring campaign effectiveness pose significant business challenges (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Appel et al., 2020; Chaffey & Chadwick, 2015). Studying customer engagement is crucial because it directly translates to customer loyalty and brand advocacy (Ertemel et al., 2021; Kumar, 2020; Ferguson et al., 2006). There is a wealth of research on SMM and CE, but a gap exists in understanding these dynamics within the specific context of a particular industry and location.

Customer engagement issues vary globally and are influenced by cultural norms, technological access, and communication styles. Like the United States, individualistic cultures require personalized approaches that cater to individual needs (Shan et al., 2023; Tikhomirova et al., 2021; Aguirre et al., 2015; Hofstede, 1984). In contrast, Asian collectivistic cultures might require fostering a sense of community (Sugimura et al., 2022; Cherry, 2022; Liu, 2020). Communication styles also play a role. High-context cultures like Japan necessitate subtle engagement strategies that respect indirect communication (Hall, 1976), while low-context cultures like Germany favor directness. Privacy regulations in Europe can restrict data collection for personalization (European Commission, 2016). On the other hand, limitations in technology infrastructure in developing countries might necessitate focusing on offline channels like SMS marketing or in-store experiences (Kumari & Singh, 2023; Lambrechts et al., 2019; World Bank Group, 2016).

While social media offers a powerful tool for engagement, concerns arise around privacy and confidentiality. Customers are increasingly cautious of brands that may exploit personal data for targeted advertising. The study of Kvalnes (2019) emphasized the ethical dilemmas faced by companies using social media. Furthermore, the pressure of brands to continuously produce engaging content can sometimes result in inauthentic portrayals, which, as Eigenramm et al. (2021) suggested, can backfire and lead to customer disengagement if perceived as inauthentic. Thanvaracorn et al. (2019) also explore the concept of 'inauthentic engagement,' highlighting how self-presentation in consumer engagement behavior can affect the authenticity of brand interactions.

In the Philippines, there is a boast of a high social media penetration rate; however, customer engagement presents unique challenges. The digital divide can hinder online engagement strategies (Astoriano et al., 2022; Conoza, 2021). Furthermore, Filipinos often value personal connections and prefer face-to-face interactions (dela Vega et al., 2017), making it challenging to shift customer service and engagement online completely.

Language also poses a hurdle. While Filipino and English are widely spoken, a significant portion of the population speaks neither fluently. To ensure effective communication, businesses must navigate this multilingual landscape (PITON Global, 2024). Culturally, the emphasis on respect and smooth interpersonal relations necessitates customer service approaches sensitive to these nuances (Rabo & Ang, 2018; Jocano, 1966). Filipino consumers are

highly price-sensitive, prioritizing the value of money. Engagement strategies must balance brand building and offering attractive deals and promotions (Inquiro, 2024; Castillo, 2018).

Despite extensive research, there remains a need for localized studies examining the influence of social media marketing in the context of health and wellness industries in the Philippines, particularly in Island Garden City of Samal. This study seeks to determine the influence of social media marketing on customer engagement, providing insights into the city's unique market dynamics. Specifically, this study aimed to address the following objectives: (1) to determine the level of social media marketing in terms of interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word of mouth; (2) to determine the level of customer engagement in terms of conscious attention, enthused participation, and social connection; (3) to determine the significant relationship between social media marketing and customer engagement; and (4) to determine the domain of social media marketing that best predicts customer engagement.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative, descriptive-correlational research method to determine the level of social media marketing and customer engagement in Zynergia, a health and wellness hub in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. The relationship between the two variables was also sought. A correlational study is a research design examining the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational studies are non-experimental, meaning the researcher does not manipulate or control any variables (Bhandari, 2023; Cherry, 2023; Monteroso et al., 2023).

2.2 Research Respondents

The study respondents are Zynergia customers. The researchers chose 53 customers using quota sampling. Quota sampling was used since no sampling frame was available. It helped the researchers obtain a sample that is as representative as possible of the population being studied (Nikolopoulou, 2023). Various studies mentioned that a sample size between 30 and 500 at a 5% significance level is generally sufficient for many researchers (Delice, 2010) cited in Morales et al. (2024) and if parametric tests are to be employed, 30 – 500 subjects would be the necessary sample size (Bacala et al., 2024; Ross, 2020; Yildirim & Şimşek, 2006; Baykul, 1999).

2.3 Research Instruments

Two sets of questionnaires were adapted from authors of different studies, which experts in questionnaire construction validated. The adapted standardized questionnaire is valid in contents as it underwent a series of modifications to classify the most reliable and valid questions. Further, the authors have already tested and proven it. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of expert validators to provide the respondents with ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the study's objective.

The first part of the questionnaire deals with social media marketing with subscales of interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word of mouth (Kim & Ko, 2012). The items were distributed to the following subscales: Interaction (4 items), Entertainment (4 items), Trend (2 items), Customization (5 items) and Word of Mouth (3 items). This 18-item survey utilized a 5-point rating scale (from Very Low to Very High).

The second set of instrument used is to measure the customer engagement of the respondents. The questionnaire was adapted from the study of Vivek et al. (2014). There were three subscales: conscious attention, enthused participation, and social connection. On this variable, each indicator is composed of the following items: Conscious Attention (6 items), Enthused Participation (7 items), and Social Connection (3 items), with a total of 15 items. This 16-item survey used a 5-point Likert Scale (from Very Low to Very High).

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Dean of the College and the School Principal; after the approval, the letter was sent to the owner of Zynergia before the administration of the research instruments. Consent was also sought from the respondents for voluntary participation. Respondents were given ample time to complete the tool. The instruments were retrieved immediately after the respondents had answered the tool entirely. After gathering the necessary data, these were tabulated, subjected to statistical treatment, and interpreted accordingly.

2.5 Statistical Tools

Mean. This was used to determine the level of social media marketing and customer engagement in a health and wellness hub.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. This was used to determine the relationship between social media marketing and customer engagement.

Multiple Linear Regression. This was used to determine which domain of social media marketing best influences customer engagement.

3. Results and Discussion

Level Social Media Marketing

Presented in Table 1 is the level of social media marketing of the health and wellness hub. Data revealed that the interaction ($M=3.65$, $SD=1.08$), entertainment ($M=3.61$, $SD=1.12$), trend ($M=3.70$, $SD=1.09$), customization ($M=3.69$, $SD=1.12$), and word-of-mouth ($M=3.60$, $SD=1.10$) were described as high which means that these domains of social media marketing were oftentimes manifested.

Table 1. Level of Social Media Marketing

Indicators	SD	M	Descriptive Level
Interaction	1.08	3.65	High
Entertainment	1.12	3.61	High
Trend	1.09	3.70	High
Customization	1.12	3.69	High
Word-of-Mouth	1.10	3.60	High
Overall Mean	1.06	3.65	High

Note: N = 53, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

On the other hand, the trend ($M=3.70$, $SD=1.09$) got the highest mean, which was described as high, which means that this domain was oftentimes manifested. This implies that leveraging trends is a common and potentially powerful strategy for social media marketing. This aligns with various studies' findings that emphasize the importance of trends in capturing user attention and engagement. Incorporating trending topics and themes into social media content can significantly boost user attention and engagement. People are naturally drawn to what is popular and exciting, and social media platforms often prioritize trending content to keep users engaged (Jha & Verma, 2024; Xin & Lim, 2023; Yang & Peng, 2022).

By aligning trends, businesses can augment their social media reach and visibility. Trending topics act as conversation starters, and businesses capitalize on themselves within relevant online discussions, attracting a wider audience (Henderson, 2024; Joshi et al., 2023). Trends often present fleeting opportunities to connect with audiences. Businesses that are quick to identify and integrate trending themes into their social media content can create a sense of timeliness and relevance, fostering a connection with their target audience (Bashar et al., 2024; Joshi et al., 2023; Mittal et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2021).

The overall mean was described as high or oftentimes manifested. This means that the social media marketing of the health and wellness hub was often observed in terms of interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word of mouth. The result suggests a multi-faceted approach where the hub utilizes interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word-of-mouth encouragement to engage its audience. This diverse strategy creates opportunities for well-rounded customer engagement, fostering a two-way communication channel and building stronger relationships. Various studies (Banerji & Singh, 2024; Hasan et al., 2023; Oscarius Yudhi Ari Wijaya et al., 2021; Wibowo et al., 2020) supported this diverse strategy as the potential for creating well-rounded customer engagement and fostering stronger relationships.

Level of Customer Engagement

Presented in Table 2 is the level of customer engagement of the health and wellness hub. Data revealed that conscious attention ($M=3.77$, $SD=.94$) and social connection ($M=3.50$, $SD=1.29$) were described as high, meaning that these customer engagement domains were oftentimes manifested. However, enthused participation as a domain of customer engagement got a mean score ($M=3.37$, $SD=1.21$) which was described as moderate or sometimes manifested.

Table 2. Level of Customer Engagement

Indicators	SD	M	Descriptive Level
Conscious Attention	.94	3.77	High
Enthused Participation	1.21	3.37	Moderate
Social Connection	1.29	3.50	High
Overall Mean	1.09	3.55	High

Note: N = 53, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

It was revealed that conscious attention got the highest mean score, described as high or oftentimes manifested. This implies that customers are actively and deliberately engaging with the business. Conscious attention suggests that customers are not passively receiving information but are actively processing and interacting with it. This level of engagement is highly beneficial for businesses as it indicates a deeper level of interest and involvement

from the customer. It could lead to stronger customer loyalty, higher customer satisfaction, and potentially increased sales and profitability. Furthermore, it suggests that the business's engagement strategies effectively capture and hold customer attention. This could provide valuable insights for future marketing and engagement strategies. Various studies (Ojha et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2021; Vivek et al., 2014) indicated similar results and highlighted the active and deliberate customer engagement with the business.

However, enthused participation got a mean score that was described as moderate or sometimes manifested. This suggests an underlying interest and engagement that fluctuates. Customers likely value the hub's offerings, but their enthusiasm could be more consistently high. There could be several reasons for this variation. Personal schedules, external obligations, and even fluctuating motivation levels can lead to inconsistent engagement. For instance, someone might be enthusiastic when starting at the hub due to the novelty, but this enthusiasm might wane during periods with less engaging activities. Alternatively, customers might prioritize the hub highly at times but need to balance it with other commitments, resulting in a moderate participation level. Various studies (Blake et al., 2024; Putra et al., 2024; Thompson et al., 2023; Camitan et al., 2021; Cvenkel (2021); South et al., 2021; Settapani et al., 2019) have parallel results.

The overall result ($M=3.55$, $SD=1.09$) was described as high. This indicates that the hub's customer engagement is often manifested. The result of this study means that customers are highly engaged and invested in the hub. This suggests that customers are mentally invested in the hub, spending time thinking about its activities, products, or services. This can lead to a better understanding and appreciation of the hub's value proposition, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty (Razmus, 2021).

Further, this implies that consumers, in general, are active participants who contribute to the hub's community. This active participation can enhance the sense of community among customers, leading to increased customer retention and word-of-mouth referrals. This could also mean the hub has fostered a supportive and inclusive community. The sense of community can enhance customers' emotional attachment to the hub, thereby increasing their likelihood of patronizing and recommending it to others (Kearl, 2021; Sirviö, 2021; Martin, 2017).

Significance of the Relationship between Social Media Marketing and Customer Engagement

As shown in Table 3, the significance of the relationship between social media marketing and customer engagement is shown. Results revealed an overall r -value of .913 with a p -value of 0.000, less than the 0.05 degree of a significant relationship. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. All domains of social media marketing have a significant relationship to the domains of customer engagement. This implies that when social marketing is high, customers are more likely to engage with the business. This further means that the hub's activities and strategies on social media platforms play a crucial role in fostering interactions and building customer relationships. Social media marketing's ability to facilitate interactive communication (Malthouse et al., 2013), share engaging content (Ashley & Tuten, 2015), build communities (Brodie et al., 2013), personalize interactions (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010), and gather feedback (He et al., 2013) all contribute to heightened customer engagement.

Table 3. Significance of the Relationship between Social Media Marketing and Customer Engagement

Social Media Marketing	Customer Engagement			
	Conscious Attention	Enthused Participation	Social Connection	Overall
Interaction	.822* (.000)	.913* (.000)	.822* (.000)	.901* (.000)
Entertainment	.820* (.000)	.910* (.000)	.853* (.000)	.912* (.000)
Trend	.787* (.000)	.852* (.000)	.816* (.000)	.866* (.000)
Customization	.782* (.000)	.866* (.000)	.792* (.000)	.860* (.000)
Word-of-Mouth	.807* (.000)	.880* (.000)	.785* (.000)	.870* (.000)
Overall	.832* (.000)	.915* (.000)	.843* (.000)	.913* (.000)

* $p < .05$ – Significant

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Customer Engagement

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis that revealed which indicator of social media marketing best influences customer engagement. The data in Table 4 shows a significant influence of social media marketing on customer engagement. The obtained F-value of 75.995 is significant at $p < 0.05$, which indicates a model fit. Also, an R-squared value of .878 or 87.8% suggested that the variance (F) in customer engagement was attributed to the indicators of social media marketing specified in this study. This means that .122 or 12.2% of the variance could be credited to other things that are already beyond the concern of this study.

Since the focal point of this section was to determine the domain of social media marketing that best influences customer engagement, the data show that entertainment, interaction, and customization were significant predictors of customer engagement. However, interaction best influences customer engagement. Interaction obtained a β -coefficient value of .827 with a corresponding computed t-value of 5.409 and p-value of < 0.001 . It can be noted that the probability value of interaction is lower than the p-value of 0.05, which was set as the significance level in this study.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Customer Engagement

Social Media Marketing	Customer Engagement		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant	.087	.454	.652
Entertainment	.658	3.621	<.001*
Interaction	.827	5.409	<.001*
Trend	.259	1.714	.093
Customization	-.432	-2.536	.015*
Word-of-Mouth	-.360	-1.923	.061
<i>R</i>	.943		
<i>R</i> ²	.878		
F	75.995		
p	.000*		

The result signifies that interaction is a pivotal aspect of social media marketing that significantly influences customer engagement. It can be said that interaction influences customer engagement by enabling two-way communication (Mangold & Faulds, 2009), real-time interactions (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2015), personalized responses (Malthouse et al., 2013), active customer feedback and participation (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004), and community building (Brodie et al., 2013). These interactive elements create a dynamic and engaging environment that fosters deeper relationships between brands and customers, driving higher levels of engagement.

However, it is essential to emphasize that customization negatively influences customer engagement. This suggests that attempts to tailor or personalize products, services, or marketing efforts to individual customer's preferences and needs had an adverse effect on their level of engagement with the brand. This counterintuitive outcome might arise from several factors, such as perceived invasiveness (Awad & Krishnan, 2006), misalignment with customer expectations (Tam & Ho, 2006), or execution flaws in the customization process (Tucker, 2014).

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The level of social marketing was described as high or oftentimes manifested. This means that the social media marketing of the health and wellness hub was often observed in terms of interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word of mouth. The result suggests a multi-faceted approach where the hub utilizes interaction, entertainment, trend, customization, and word-of-mouth encouragement to engage its audience.
2. The level of customer engagement was described as high. This indicates that the hub's customer engagement is often manifested. The result of this study means that customers are highly engaged and invested in the hub. This suggests that customers are mentally invested in the hub, spending time thinking about its activities, products, or services.
3. There was a significant relationship between service quality and customer engagement. This implies that when social marketing is high, customers are more likely to engage with the business. This further means that the hub's activities and strategies on social media platforms play a crucial role in fostering interactions and building customer relationships.

4. Among the domains of social media marketing, interaction best influences customer engagement. This implies that social media marketing thrives on interaction. It is a conversation that fosters a community and allows businesses to tailor content for better engagement. Businesses create a positive experience that keeps customers returning by interacting and addressing concerns. This also suggests that out of various strategies and activities employed in social media marketing, interactive elements such as two-way communication, real-time responses, and active participation are the most effective in driving customer engagement.

After a careful review of the conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. Management is recommended to enhance further interactive engagement by providing staff training for social media interactions and fostering online communities for customer interaction. They may create varied and engaging videos (e.g., videos and stories) and encourage and highlight user-generated content. Additionally, the management is recommended to monitor and incorporate current social media trends and launch innovative and timely marketing campaigns. They may implement feedback to tailor services and marketing efforts and promote customer testimonials and reviews. The management may actively seek and highlight customer testimonials and reviews.
2. The customers are recommended to engage actively in social media activities (e.g., comments, shares, and live sessions), provide feedback and suggestions for service improvements, and share personal experiences and success stories related to the hub's services on social media.
3. Future researchers are encouraged to investigate the specific impact of each social media marketing domain on customer engagement. They may conduct studies over time to examine how the effectiveness of social media marketing evolves. They may also compare the influence of social media marketing across different industries or types of health and wellness hubs. Future researchers may explore customer motivations, preferences, and behaviors in response to various social media marketing strategies. Additionally, they may examine the role of emerging technologies in enhancing the effectiveness of social media marketing efforts.

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